

First helminthological data on Iberian vipers: helminth communities and host-parasite relationships

Xavier Santos^{1,2}, Fernando Martínez-Freiría³, Juan M. Pleguezuelos¹ and Vicente Roca⁴

¹ Dpto. Biología Animal y Ecología, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Granada.
18071 Granada.

² Dpto. Biología Animal, Facultad de Biología, Universidad de Barcelona.
Avgda. Diagonal 645, 08028 Barcelona.

³ Dpto. Biología Animal, Facultad de Biología, Universidad de Salamanca. Campus
Miguel de Unamuno, Edificio de Farmacia, 37007 Salamanca.

⁴ Dpto. Zoología, Facultad de Ciencias Biológicas, Universidad de Valencia.
C/ Dr. Moliner 50, 46100 Burjassot, Valencia.

Address for correspondence: X. Santos, Dpto. Biología Animal y Ecología, Facultad de
Ciencias, Universidad de Granada. 18071 Granada, Tel: +34-58-243082, Fax: +34-58-
243238, E-mail: xsantos1@ugr.es.

Key words: Nematodes, helminths, parasitism, *Vipera aspis*, *Vipera latastei*, Iberian
Peninsula.

Running head: Helminths in *Vipera aspis* and *V. latastei*

Abstract. European vipers are ambush predators with sporadic feeding events, thereby maintaining the digestive tract empty for long periods. According to previous studies relating lizards' dietary habits and their helminth faunas, we predict poor gastrointestinal helminth communities in vipers. To test this hypothesis, we have examined the digestive tract of 86 specimens of *Vipera latastei* Boscá, 1878, and *V. aspis* (Linnaeus, 1758) from several localities of the Iberian Peninsula. We found only two adult nematode species *Kalicephalus viperae* (Rudolphi, 1819) and *Ophidascaris* sp. Baylis, 1921, and cysts adhering to the external wall on the stomach of two other nematode species *Ascarops strongylina* (Rudolphi, 1819) and *Agamospirura* sp. Henry et Sisoff, 1913. All these nematodes are common parasite species in snakes, although *Ophidascaris* sp. has never before been recorded in *Vipera* sp. The low prevalence and small number of parasite species in Iberian vipers matched their low feeding rates. However, our results contrast with studies in Poland and Belarus of *V. berus* species, in which nematodes as well as trematodes are common and abundant. Rainfall rates are lower in the Iberian Peninsula than eastern Central Europe, where amphibians are more available and consumed for *V. berus*. Amphibians, intermediate hosts for these platyhelminths, have been recorded only sporadically as prey for *V. aspis* and *V. latastei*, thus supporting the absence of trematodes in both Iberian viper species. Among populations of Iberian vipers, the prevalence of parasites correlates with the feeding rate (i.e. percentage of vipers with prey), suggesting a linkage between the two parameters. In conclusion, our results suggest that several factors, including climatic characteristics of localities, feeding rates of predators, and type of prey consumed, influence the number and type of parasites in Iberian vipers.

Studies on the community ecology of parasites in European reptiles have increased in the last decade (Martin and Roca 2005), one of the most novel topics is the relationship between host diet and helminth communities (Roca 1999). Correlations between parasites and host diet have been widely examined in lizards (Dearing 1993, Roca 1996, 1999), and differences between the helminth communities parasitizing herbivorous and carnivorous reptiles have been intensely studied (Petter and Quentin 1976, Martin et al. 2005). For example, herbivorous reptiles have richer and more diverse helminth communities than do carnivorous reptiles, and also harbour many nematode species (Roca 1999, Roca et al. 2005). Furthermore, differences in helminth faunas have been shown among lizards with different types of feeding strategies: sit and wait (ambush predator) species have poorer helminth communities than do widely foraging predators (Roca 1999). Unfortunately, snakes have received less attention in this sense (Aho 1990). Although strictly carnivorous, snakes can also be used as a model to test helminth differences according to dietary habits and foraging modes. Hence, ambush predators that consume a low number of prey per year become an extreme strategy that would presumably be correlated with their helminth fauna. For these species, we predict poor gastrointestinal helminth communities according to dietary habits characterized by long periods without feeding as they forage on few and voluminous prey (Greene 1997). European vipers conform well with this prediction, being ambush predators (Bea et al. 1992) with very low feeding rates (Saint Girons 1979, 1980b). Although the feeding ecology of several European vipers is well known (e.g. Braña et al. 1987, Bea and Braña 1988, Luiselli and Agrimi 1991, Agrimi and Luiselli 1992, Brito 2004), their helminth communities are known only for some populations of the eastern Central Europe (Lewin and Grabda-Kazubska 1997, Shimalov and Shimalov 2000, Borkovcová and Kopriva 2005). In the Iberian Peninsula,

three viper species cohabitate in parapatric distributions: *Vipera seoanei* (Lataste, 1879) in the north-western corner, *V. aspis* (Linnaeus, 1758) in the north-central and north-eastern belt, and *V. latastei* Boscá, 1878 in the rest of the Iberian Peninsula (Pleguezuelos et al. 2002). Despite this diversity, the parasites of Iberian vipers have never been examined.

In this paper, we present the first helminthological data for several locations of two of these species, *V. aspis* and *V. latastei*, inhabiting sharply contrasting climatic areas. The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between the helminth community and dietary parameters of *V. aspis* and *V. latastei*, specifically addressing the following issues: (i) characterization of the patterns of helminth diversity in both host species; (ii) determination of eventual relationships between helminths and dietary patterns; (iii) analysis of the factors (geographic, sexual, and ontogenetic) which affect parasitism rates in the Iberian vipers; and (iv) comparison of helminthological data of these hosts with those of other European vipers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We analysed the digestive tract of 86 road-killed specimens of two Iberian vipers, *V. aspis* and *V. latastei*, collected in three geographic areas: eastern Andalusia (SE Spain), Catalonia (NE Spain) and the north-western part of Burgos province (N Spain; see Fig. 1 for partial sample sizes and geographic situation of the areas). *V. aspis* and *V. latastei* are small and stout-bodied viviparous snakes. *V. aspis* is distributed throughout central and southern Europe; in the Iberian Peninsula, it occurs only in the north-eastern sector (the Pyrenees, Pre-Pyrenees, and foothills of Cantabrian chain and the north of the Iberian Mountain Range) (Gosá 2002, Fig. 1). *V. latastei* occurs throughout most of the Iberian Peninsula, except for a narrow strip in the north where *V.*

seoanei and *V. aspis* are present, and in North Africa, along some of the mountainous chains, from northern Morocco to northern Tunisia (Pleguezuelos and Santos 2002). As in other Eurasian vipers, their distribution is essentially parapatric (Duguy et al. 1979, Saint Girons 1980a), although there are some zones of contact, as in northern Burgos province, where the two species are found in sympatry (Barbadillo 1983).

Specimens were measured (snout-vent length, SVL in mm), dissected, and sexed by examination of gonads. When the digestive tract was removed, both the stomach and intestine were checked for prey. Recent prey in the stomach were easily identified, while prey in the intestine were determined by hair (for mammals) or scales (for reptiles) at 400X.

After the prey were removed, the digestive tract was analysed for the presence of helminths. Once detected, helminths were removed, washed, fixed and mounted according to standard techniques (for details see Roca 1985). When possible, parasites were identified to the species, and the number and location within the viper's gut recorded.

The use of descriptive ecological terms (i.e. prevalence of infection, intensity and abundance of parasites) followed Bush et al. (1997). Parasites were classified as satellite, secondary, and core species according to their prevalence in the hosts: a prevalence of 10% was adopted as the lowest limit in identifying satellite species (Kennedy and Bakke 1989); species with 10-30% of prevalence were considered secondary species (Hanski 1982, Roca 1993); and species with a prevalence of 30% or higher were deemed core species (Roca 1993). Brillouin's index was used for calculating diversity according to Magurran (2004). Contingency tables and Monte Carlo simulation for estimates of homogeneity among samples were performed with CHRXC software (Zaykin and Pudovkin 1993).

RESULTS

Four helminth species (all nematodes) were found parasitizing both *V. aspis* and *V. latastei* (Table 1). The position in the viper's gut, and the infection parameters for each host species, are shown in Table 2. The overall prevalence of infection in *V. latastei* was 16.4% with inter-population differences (Andalusia 16.3%, Catalonia 33.3%, and Burgos 0.0%) close to significance (3x2 Table $\chi^2 = 4.86$, $P = 0.075$, $n = 67$). The overall prevalence of infection of *V. aspis* was 26.3%, differences between populations being significant (Catalonia 50%, Burgos 9.1%, 2x2 Table $\chi^2 = 4.0$, $P = 0.0456$, $n = 19$). No interspecific differences were found between the two *Vipera* species in the prevalence of infection (2x2 Table $\chi^2 = 0.96$, $P = 0.33$, $n = 86$).

Helminth infracommunities of *V. latastei* were comprised of two species of adult nematodes and two species of nematodes in larval stages. Adult nematodes were *Kalicephalus viperae* (Rudolphi, 1819) and *Ophidascaris* sp. Baylis, 1921, both found into the digestive tract (Table 2). In one host, a large number of *Ophidascaris* sp. were found occluding the final portion of the large intestine. Larval forms of *Ascarops strongylina* (Rudolphi, 1819) and *Agamospirura* sp. Henry et Sisoff, 1913 were found inside small cysts of conjunctive tissue adhering to the external wall of the stomach. The mean values of the species richness and abundance for *V. aspis* and *V. latastei* were, respectively, 0.18 (SD = 0.42, range = 0 – 2), and 0.58 (SD = 2.98, range = 0 – 24). The mean value of Brillouin's index of diversity for each individual was 0.002 (SD = 0.016, range = 0 – 0.132). Mean values of parasitism diversity parameters for *V. aspis* were not calculated due the very poor helminth infracommunities in this species.

All the specimens of both host species with parasites in the digestive tract were sexually mature, and none of the 19 juveniles of both viper species had digestive

parasites. The adult vipers from Andalusia had no sexual differences in the prevalence of helminths in the digestive tract (2x2 Table $\chi^2 = 0.89$, $P = 0.35$, $n = 36$), either in the presence of helminths between vipers with or without prey in the digestive tract (2x2 Table $\chi^2 = 0.01$, $P = 0.94$, $n = 43$). However, in a comparison among all populations of both species, those populations exhibiting higher feeding rates (i.e. higher percentage of vipers with prey) had more prevalence of helminth parasites in the digestive tract (Fig. 2), although this pattern was not statistically significant after arcsine-transformed percentages, perhaps due to the small sample size (R Spearman $R = 0.7$, $P = 0.19$, $n = 5$).

DISCUSSION

Since *V. latastei* and *V. aspis* had never before been helminthologically investigated in Iberian Peninsula (Lluch et al. 1987), the four nematode species mentioned here are new records for Iberian vipers. Three of these helminth species, *Kalicephalus viperae*, *Ascarops strongylina* (larvae) and *Agamospirura* sp. (larvae) are common species in other European vipers (Sharpilo 1976). Ascaridoid nematodes of *Ophidascaris* spp. are commonly found parasitizing snakes worldwide (Martins et al. 2003) although they have not been recorded in *Vipera* spp. (Yorke and Maplestone 1969, Sprent 1984). Thus, this is the first record of this nematode genus in snakes of the genus *Vipera*.

The parasites *K. viperae* and *Ophidascaris* sp. can be considered snake specialists (*sensu* Edwards and Bush 1989) since they parasitize only this group of reptiles (Yorke and Maplestone 1969, Sharpilo 1976), whereas *A. strongylina* and *Agamospirura* sp. (larvae) appear to be generalist species as they also parasitize other reptiles such as lizards and skinks (Sharpilo 1976).

In the Iberian viper species here considered, all nematode species occurred at low prevalence. No core or secondary species could be identified, and only *Ophidascaris* sp. from *V. aspis* could be considered a satellite species (Kennedy and Bakke 1989). The low values of prevalence and mean intensity of infection (Table 2) indicate that many members of the helminth infracommunities (all of them in the case of *V. aspis*) occur only irregularly and occasionally (Martin and Roca 2005). This disagrees with the typical pattern of helminth infection in many reptiles, characterized by the following patterns: i) few species occurring frequently, ii) few species occurring with moderate prevalence, and iii) many species appearing, but in very low proportion (Aho 1990, Martin and Roca 2005). Furthermore, our results contrast with other European and American vipers (Lewin and Grabda-Kazubska 1997, Dias et al. 2004). For example, recent studies on helminth communities of *Vipera berus* in Eastern Europe showed that this viper harboured 19 and 13 helminth species in Poland and Belarus, respectively (Lewin and Grabda-Kazubska 1997, Shimalov and Shimalov 2000).

Both *V. aspis* and *V. latastei* do not usually feed on amphibians (Bea 1998, unpublished data of authors), and this would be the reason for the absence of trematodes as viper parasites, as these platyhelminths frequently use amphibians as intermediate hosts (see Dollfus 1954). In a current study including 347 *V. latastei* specimens throughout the Iberian Peninsula, only 1.7% of prey were amphibians, all of them belonging to vipers collected in rainy areas (more than 2000 mm annual rainfall). By contrast, in a Polish population, 15.9% of the prey of *V. berus* were amphibians (Pomianowska-Philipiuk 1974), this correlating with the high presence of trematodes in the digestive tract of this species. Nine trematode species have been found parasitizing *V. berus* in Poland (Lewin and Grabda-Kazubska 1997), eight of which were found in the same host in Belarus (Shimalov and Shimalov 2000). In both areas, the trematode

Alaria alata was the helminth with the highest prevalence rate, and was associated with the consumption of amphibians by vipers (Lewin and Grabda-Kazubska 1997, Shimalov and Shimalov 2000). Habitats occupied by *V. latastei* and *V. berus* in the Iberian Peninsula and Eastern Europe, respectively, are different. In Poland and Belarus, habitats are wetter than those inhabited by Iberian vipers, this allowing higher availability of amphibians as prey for vipers. This confirms that physiography (and also temperature and moisture) are critical factors explaining differences in helminth infections of reptile hosts (Martin and Roca 2004).

Availability of intermediate hosts may be another factor involving the differences between *V. latastei* and *V. aspis* from the Iberian Peninsula, and *V. berus* from Eastern Europe. Thus, the distribution of *Ophidascaris* spp. in snakes is limited by this factor (Sprent 1984). On the other hand, when the snakes are parathenic or intermediate hosts for helminth species (*Ascarops strongylina* and *Agamospirura* sp. in the case of Iberian vipers), the diversity and abundance of larval helminths depends upon the overlap in the host range with other vertebrates (mammals and birds) that support the species in the region (Sharpilo et al. 2001). Mammals such as the wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) and the hedgehog (*Erinaceus europaeus*) have been recorded as predators of *V. latastei* and *V. aspis* in Spain (Bea 1998, Bea and Braña 1998), adults of *Ascarops strongylina* being common parasites of wild boars and domestic pigs (Yamaguti 1961).

Regarding the diversity of the helminth community of *V. latastei*, the mean value of Brillouin's diversity index has proved to be one of the lowest among all values known for European reptiles (Roca and Hornero 1994, Biserkov and Kostadinova 1998, Roca 1999, Sanchis et al. 2000, Martin and Roca 2004, 2005). Brillouin's index was lower only in the case of *Podarcis carbonelli* (Sauria: Lacertidae) from a peculiar area of northwest Portugal (Galdón et al., unpublished data). This low diversity, which

agrees with the general pattern found in snakes (Aho 1990), might be explained in the following terms: (i) Iberian vipers occupy drier habitats than other European vipers, hosts associated with aquatic habitats harbouring richer and more diverse communities than terrestrial reptile hosts (Aho 1990); this also agrees with results for *Natrix maura* (aquatic snake) from Spain, which shows more rich and diverse helminth communities than the terrestrial snakes here studied (Navarro et al. 1987); (ii) few interactions with other reptile and amphibian species, in the studied populations (see Sanchis et al. 2000); (iii) low feeding rate, offering less opportunities for recruitment of parasites; (iv) other general features of reptile hosts, such as ectothermy, simplicity of the alimentary canal, and low vagility, all of these exhibited by vipers (Kennedy et al. 1986, Aho 1990, Roca and Hornero 1994, Martin and Roca 2004).

The Iberian vipers exhibit low values of prevalence of gastrointestinal helminths and poor helminth infracommunities, which matched well with the low feeding rates and ambush predation (low vagility) of these snakes. In fact, *V. latastei* concentrates feeding activity in a low period (from June to August in males, and from April-May up to October in females according to their reproductive status; Saint Girons 1980b, Brito 2003, unpublished data of authors). Among Iberian populations, differences in the parasitism rates apparently correlated with differences in feeding rates (Fig. 2), suggesting a linkage in the feeding habits/rates and presence and frequency of gastrointestinal parasites, as reported in lizards (see Roca 1999). However, European vipers of similar life-history traits (e.g. *V. berus*) show higher rates of parasitism than in the Iberian populations. Thus, the differences in the number of parasites among viper populations and species could be explained by several biotic and abiotic characteristics of the hosts.

Acknowledgements. We thank M. García Paris for his logistic support in the analysis of vipers. X. Santos was supported by a post-doctoral grant (EX2003/0253) and F. Martínez-Freiría by a pre-doctoral grant (FPU nº AP2003-2633) from Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte (Spain) This research was partially funded by the project REN2000-1376 GLO of the Spanish MCYT to J.M. Pleguezuelos.

REFERENCES

- AGRIMI U., LUISELLI. L. 1992: Feeding strategies of the viper *Vipera ursinii ursinii* (Reptilia: Viperidae) in the Apennines. Herpetol. J. 2: 37-42.
- AHO J.M. 1990: Helminth communities of amphibians and reptiles: Comparative approaches to understanding patterns and processes. In: G. Esch, A. Bush and J. Aho (Eds.), Parasite communities: patterns and processes. Chapman and Hall, London. pp. 157-195,
- BARBADILLO L.J. 1983: Sobre la distribución de anfibios y reptiles en la provincia de Burgos. Butll. Soc. Cat. Ictio. Herp. 5: 10- 17.
- BEA A. 1998: *Vipera aspis*. In: A. Salvador (Coordinador), M.A. Ramos et al. (Eds.), Reptiles. Fauna Ibérica, vol. 10, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, pp. 469-480..
- BEA A., BRAÑA F. 1988: Nota sobre la alimentación de *Vipera latastei*, Boscá, 1878 (Reptilia, Viperidae). Munibe 40: 121-124.
- BEA A., BRAÑA F. 1998: *Vipera latasti*. In: A. Salvador (Coordinador), M.A. Ramos et al. (Eds.), Reptiles. Fauna Ibérica, vol. 10, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, pp. 480-488.
- BEA A., BRAÑA F., BARÓN J.P., SAINT GIRONS H. 1992: Régimes et cycles alimentaires des vipères européennes (Reptilia, Viperidae). Ann. Biol. 31: 25-44.

- BISERKOV V., KOSTADINOVA A. 1998: Intestinal helminth communities in the green lizard, *Lacerta viridis*, from Bulgaria. *J. Helminthol.* 72: 267-271.
- BORCOVKOVÁ M., KOPRIVA J. 2005: Parasitic helminths of reptiles (Reptilia) in South Moravia (Czech Republic). *Parasitological Research* 95: 77-78.
- BRAÑA F., BEA A., SAINT GIRONS H. 1987: Composición de la dieta y ciclos de alimentación en *Vipera seoanei* Lataste, 1879. Variaciones en relación con la edad y el ciclo reproductor. *Munibe* 40: 19-27.
- BRITO J.C. 2003: Seasonal and daily activity patterns of *Vipera latastei* in northern Portugal. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 24: 497-508.
- BRITO J.C. 2004: Feeding ecology of *Vipera latastei* in northern Portugal: ontogenetic shifts, prey size and seasonal differences. *Herpetol. J.* 14: 13-19.
- BUSH A.O., LAFERTY K.D., LOFT J.M., SHOSTAK, A.W. 1997: Parasitology meets ecology on its own terms: Margolis *et al.* revisited. *J. Parasitol.* 83: 575-583.
- DEARING M.D. 1993: An alimentary specialization for herbivory in the tropical whiptail lizard *Cnemidophorus murinus*. *J. Herpetol.* 27: 111-114.
- DIAS R.J.P., ALMEIDA S.B.J., PRIETO D.B., DE SOUZA LIMA S. 2004: Aspectos ecológicos dos nematóides parasitos de *Crotalus durissus terrificus* Laurenti, 1768 (Ophidia, Viperidae), em Juiz de Fora, Minas Gerais, Brasil. *Revista Brasileira de Zociências Juiz de Fora* 6: 231-235.
- DOLLFUS R.P. 1954: *Miscellanea Helminthologica Maroccana: Présence au Maroc de Leptophallus nigrovenosus* (Bellingham) (Trématodes, Distomes). *Archives de l'Institut Pasteur du Maroc.* 6: 612-624.
- DUGUY R., MARTÍNEZ-RICA J.P., SAINT GIRONS H. 1979: La répartition des vipères dans les Pyrénées et les régions voisines du nord de l'Espagne. *Bull. Soc. Hist. Nat. Toulouse* 115(3-4): 359- 377.

- EDWARDS D.D., BUSH A.O. 1989: Helminth communities in avocets: Importance of compound community. *J. Parasitol.* 98: 439-445.
- GOSÁ A. 2002: *Vipera aspis*. In: J.M. Pleguezuelos, R. Márquez and M. Lizana (Eds.), *Atlas y Libro Rojo de los Anfibios y Reptiles de España*, DGCN - AHE, Madrid, Spain, pp. 295-297.
- GREENE H.W. 1997: *Snakes. The evolution of mystery in Nature*. University of California Press, Berkeley.
- HANSKI I. 1982: Dynamics of regional distribution: the core and satellite species hypothesis. *Oikos* 38: 210-221.
- KENNEDY C.R., BAKKE T.A. 1989: Diversity patterns in helminth communities in common gulls, *Larus canus*. *Parasitology* 98: 431-445.
- KENNEDY C.R., BUSH A.O., AHO J.M. 1986: Patterns in helminth communities: Why are birds and fish different? *Parasitology* 93: 205-215.
- LEWIN J., GRABDA-KAZUBSKA B. 1997: Parasites of *Vipera berus* L. in Poland. *Acta Parasitologica* 42: 92-96.
- LLUCH J., ROCA V., NAVARRO P., MAS-COMA S. 1987: Helminthofauna de los herpetos ibéricos: estado actual de conocimientos, consideraciones ecológicas y estimaciones crológicas. In: V. Sans-Coma, S. Mas-Coma and J. Gosálbez (Eds.), *Mamíferos y Helmintos. Volumen Homenaje al Prof. Dr. Dr. Herman Kahmann en su 81 aniversario*, Ketrés, Barcelona, pp. 143-161
- LUISELLI L., AGRIMI U. 1991: Composition and variation of the diet of *Vipera aspis franciscirerdi* in relation to age and reproductive stage. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 12: 137-144.
- MAGURRAN A.E. 2004: *Measuring biological diversity*. Blackwell Publishing, Malden.

- MARTIN J.E., ROCA V. 2004: Helminth infracommunities of *Gallotia caesaris caesaris* and *Gallotia caesaris gomerae* (Sauria: Lacertidae) from the Canary Islands (Eastern Atlantic). *J. Parasitol.* 90: 266-270.
- MARTIN J.E., ROCA V. 2005: Helminths of the Atlantic lizard, *Gallotia atlantica* (Reptilia: Lacertidae), in the Canary Islands (Eastern Atlantic): composition and structure of component communities. *Acta Parasitologica* 50: 85-89.
- MARTIN J.E., LLORENTE G.A., ROCA V., CARRETERO M.A., MONTORI A., SANTOS X., ROMEU R. 2005: Relationships between diet and helminths in *Gallotia caesaris* (Sauria: Lacertidae). *Zoology*.
- MARTINS M.H., CORREIA DOS SANTOS L., VICENTE J.J., MUÑIZ-PEREIRA L.C., MAGALHAES R. 2003: *Ophidascaris durissus* sp. nov. (Nematoda, Ascarididae) parasitizing *Crotalus durissus* Linnaeus (Ophidia, Viperidae) in Brazil. *Revista Brasileira de Zoología* 20: 9-11.
- NAVARRO P., LLUCH J., ROCA V. 1987: Contribución al conocimiento de la helmintofauna de los herpetos ibéricos. VI. Parásitos de *Natrix maura* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Reptilia: Colubridae). *Revista Ibérica de Parasitología* 47: 65-70.
- PETTER A.J., QUENTIN J.C. 1976: Keys to genera of the Oxyuroidea. In: R.C. Anderson, A.G. Chabaud, S. Willmott (Eds.), *CIH Keys to the nematode parasites of vertebrates*, CAB International, London, pp. 1-30.
- PLEGUEZUELOS J.M., MÁRQUEZ R., LIZANA M. (eds.) 2002: Atlas y Libro Rojo de los Anfibios y Reptiles de España. DGCN-AHE, Madrid, 585 pp.
- PLEGUEZUELOS J.M., SANTOS X. 2002: *Vipera latasti*. In: J.M. Pleguezuelos, R. Márquez and M. Lizana (Eds.), Atlas y Libro Rojo de los Anfibios y Reptiles de España, DGCN - AHE, Madrid, Spain, pp. 298-300.

- POMIANOWSKA-PHILIPUK I. 1974: Energy balance and food requirements of adult vipers (*Vipera berus*, L.). *Ekologia Polska* 22: 195-211.
- ROCA V. 1985: Contribución al conocimiento de la helmintofauna de los Lacértidos y Gekónidos del piso termomediterráneo del Levante ibérico. PhD. Thesis, Faculty of Biological Sciences, University of Valencia, Valencia, 486 pp.
- ROCA V. 1993: Helmintofauna dels reptils. *Monografies de la Societat d'Història Natural de les Balears* 2: 273-292.
- ROCA V. 1996: The effect of some factors on the helminth parasite infracommunities of *Podarcis* lizards in the Balearic Islands (Western Mediterranean). *Bolletí de la Societat d'Història Natural de les Balears* 39: 65-76.
- ROCA V. 1999: Relación entre las faunas endoparásitas de reptiles y su tipo de alimentación. *Rev. Esp. Herpetol.* 13: 101-121.
- ROCA V., HORNERO M.J. 1994: Helminth infracommunities of *Podarcis pityusensis* and *Podarcis lilfordi* (Sauria: Lacertidae) from the Balearic Islands (western Mediterranean Basin). *Can. J. Zool.* 72: 658-664.
- ROCA V., CARRETERO M.A., LLORENTE G.A., MONTORI A., MARTIN J.E. 2005: Helminth communities of two lizard populations (Lacertidae) from Canary Islands (Spain). Host diet-parasite relationships. *Amphibia-Reptilia*.
- SAINT GIRONS H. 1979: Les cycles alimentaires des Vipères européennes dans des conditions semi-naturelles. *Ann. Biol. Anim. Bioch. Biophys.* 19(1A): 125-134.
- SAINT-GIRONS H. 1980a: Biogéographie et évolution des vipères européennes. *Comptes Rendus de la Société de Biogéographie* 496: 146- 172.
- SAINT GIRONS H. 1980b: Le cycle des mues chez les vipères européennes. *Bull. Soc. Zool. France* 105: 551-559.

- SANCHIS V., ROIG J.M., CARRETERO M.A., ROCA V., LLORENTE G.A. 2000: Host-parasite relationships of *Zootoca vivipara* (Sauria: Lacertidae) in the Pyrenees (North Spain). *Folia Parasitologica* 47: 118-122.
- SHARPILO V.P. 1976: Parasitic worms of reptiles in the USSR. Naukova Dumka, Kiev, 286 pp.
- SHARPILO V.P., BISERKOV V., KOSTADINOVA A., BEHNKE J.M., KUZMIN, Y.I. 2001: Helminths of the sand lizard, *Lacerta agilis* (Reptilia, Lacertidae), in the Palaearctic: faunal diversity and spatial patterns of variation in the composition and structure of component communities. *Parasitology* 123: 389-400.
- SHIMALOV V.V., SHIMALOV V.T. 2000: Helminth fauna of snakes (Reptilia, Serpentes) in Bielorussian Polesye. *Parasitological Research* 86: 340-341.
- SPRENT J.F.A. 1984: Ascaridoid Nematodes. In: G.L. Hoff, F. Frye and E.R. Jacobson (Eds.), *Diseases of amphibians and reptiles*. Plenum Press, New York, pp. 219-245
- YAMAGUTI S. 1961: *Systema helminthum*. Vol III. The Nematodes of Vertebrates. Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1261 pp.
- YORKE W., MAPLESTONE P.A. 1969: *The nematode parasites of vertebrates*. Hafner Publishing Company, New York, 536 pp.
- ZAYKIN D.V., PUDOVKIN A.I. 1993: Two programs to estimate significance of Chi-square values using pseudo-probability test. *J. Hered.* 84: 152.

Legends of Tables and Figures

Figure 1: Distribution of *Vipera aspis*, *V. latastei* and *V. seoanei* in the Iberian Peninsula (modified from Pleguezuelos et al., 2002), and geographic location of the five viper population examined for helminth parasites. Each population includes the viper species, sample size (n) and climatic characteristic of the population: mean scores of the altitude (alt., mean altitude in meters), annual rainfall (P) and annual temperature (T).

Figure 2: Relationship between feeding rate (percentage of vipers with prey) and parasitism rates (percentage of vipers with parasites). Each point indicates one population and its sample size. VI-C: *Vipera latastei* in Catalonia, VI-A: *V. latastei* in Andalusia, VI-B: *V. latastei* in Burgos, Va-C: *V. aspis* in Catalonia, Va-B: *V. aspis* in Burgos.

Table 1: Presence-absence of helminth species parasitizing *Vipera aspis* and *V. latastei* from the different sampling areas.

Table 2: Infection parameters of helminth species parasitizing *Vipera aspis* and *V. latastei* from the Iberian Peninsula. Diversity parameters were not calculated for *V. aspis* due to the poor helminth communities.

Figure 1: Santos et al.

Figure 2: Santos et al.

Table 1: Santos et al.

Helminth species	<i>Vipera latastei</i> (n=67)			<i>Vipera aspis</i> (n=19)	
	Andalusia	Catalonia	Burgos	Catalonia	Burgos
<i>Kalicephalus viperae</i>	*	*		*	
<i>Ophidascaris</i> sp.		*		*	
<i>Ascarops strongylina</i> (l.)	*			*	
<i>Agamospirura</i> sp. (l.)	*				*

Table 2: Santos et al.

Helminth species	Site	<i>V. latastei</i> (n=67)		<i>V. aspis</i> (n=19)
		Prevalence	Mean intensity	Mean abundance
<i>Kalicephalus viperae</i>	Oesophagus	6	4±0.6 (1-2)	0.1±0.4 (0-2)
<i>Ophidascaris</i> sp.	Intestine	3	12.5±14.8 (2-23)	0.4±2.8 (0-23)
<i>Ascarops strongylina</i> (larvae)	Body cavity	1.5	--	--
<i>Agamospirura</i> sp. (larvae)	Body cavity	7.5	1.2±0.4 (1-2)	0.1±0.3 (0-2)